

Factors Related to Behaviour Trend of Roasted Coffee Consumers

Anocha Kimkong

Abstract—The purpose of this research was to study the behavior trend factors of consumers to roasted coffee at the petrol station on the route of Rangsit to Nakhon Nayok. The research drew upon data collected from the regular consumers of roasted coffee stands. The majority of respondents was male, 33-39 years old, and holding a bachelor degree. The majority of respondents considered themselves private business proprietors or entrepreneurs and had a monthly income of between 10,000-16,000 baht. The regular coffee consumers spent a minimum coffee expense of between 45 and 300 baht per day. These consumers also displayed good attitude and good motivation which can be ranked as very high. From the hypothesis testing of the behavior trend for the roasted coffee consumers in repurchasing coffee and recommended the coffee to others, the findings revealed that it had a significant correlation. Moreover, the overall attitude towards the marketing mix factors also had a significant correlation with the behavior trend consumers.

Keywords—Factors Related, Consuming Behaviour, Coffee Consumers.

I. INTRODUCTION

FOR some time, coffee has been the well-know beverage in Thailand, it is a favorite drink with a unique, strong flavor, and lasting aroma. Nowadays, coffee is the drink of choice to replenish exhaustion. It should be noted that coffee is a major industry and receives government support. Thailand is also one of the ASEAN countries that produces much coffee, less only from Vietnam and Indonesia. Comparing to all production worldwide, Thailand can produce 80,000 tons/year which only 1.2%-1.3% of the worldwide production. Moreover, 90%-95% of Thailand's coffee is Robusta Coffee. Thai consumes coffee 30,000-50,000 tons while the rest 50,000-55,000 tons will be exported to Malaysia, Poland, Belgium, and the United State of America, etc. The exported coffees are both processed and raw coffee beans. The coffee factories are located in the southern Thailand, to buying raw coffees and produces instant coffee to sell. The Arabica coffee has a extinguished aroma and is usually cultivated in the northern Thailand due to cool temperatures. People mostly cultivate Arabica in Chiang Mai, Mae Hong Son, Trat, and Chiang Rai. The production is 800-850 tons/ year, which is only 4-5% of the overall production. Robusta, which contains few aromas is cultivated much in southern Thailand i.e. Ranong, Chomporn, Krabi and Nakorn Sithamarat. The production rate is around 95% of the total product [1].

Anocha Kimkong is with the Faculty of Management Science, Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University, Bangkok, 10300 Thailand (Corresponding author phone: 662 160 1490; fax: 662 160 1491; e-mail: k_anocha@hotmail.com).

Coffee is still maintaining its popularity and market share from various forms of productions, which were created to meet the customers' expectations i.e. instant coffee, fresh canned coffee, and roasted coffee parlors. It should be noted that the business regarding roasted coffee parlors has its roots in Thailand for over 7 years, but it has just become popular in 2010. The growth rate of the business is still continuing to increase by 10%. The growth rate can be seen from various customer groups. From the past, the main group for the business was limited only to the businessmen and travelers. But presently the target group is expanding to office people as well as students. The business regarding coffee parlors in Thailand is very interesting as it lights up many opportunities that are centered on the idea of drinking coffee for entertainment and lifestyle.

Popularity of roasted coffee parlors has caused much of intense business competition, especially for the selling channel. Many selling channel are available in the leading shopping malls. This has caused the shortage of selling area and the increasing of capital cost for expanding business branches. Other interesting locations that do not depend on the leading shopping malls are movie theatres, university campuses, hospitals, and petrol stations. In fact, coffee parlors in the petrol stations could be counted as a business with the most interesting growth rate as there is still some available room for business expansion. The business itself has less daily expenses due to using domestic raw material. The general income for the coffee parlors in the petrol stations would be around 3,000-6,000 baht daily, with 1,000 baht of profit [2]. Coffee parlors in petrol stations are counted as Small and Medium sized Enterprise (SME), which has a very interesting market and room for expansion with a large customer's base. Even though there are many numbers of coffee parlors in petrol stations, it appears that the competition rate is not so intense. In addition, there are many campaigns to support people who earn a low rate of income to build coffee parlor business. People can build their own business by investing minimum capitol thanks to those campaigns.

Route of Rangsit to Nakhon Nayok is the way from Vipawadee Rangsit to Nakron Nayok province, which is not far from Bangkok, only 107 km [3]. Nakron Nayok province is located at the east of Thailand with an area 2,122 sq.km. or about 1,326,250 Rai. To he north is Saraburee, Nakorn Sithamarat and PhachinBuri and to the west is Pathum Thani. The estimated time of traveling by car is less than half an hour from Bangkok. This route has many attractions such as Museums, Universities and various tourist attractions.

From the above information, the roasted coffee parlors operating in petrol stations on the route of Rangsit to Nakhon Nayok is very interesting to study.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. The Objectives

- 1) To study behavior trends of roasted coffee consumers at coffee parlors operate in petrol stations on the route of Rangsit to Nakhon Nayok categories by demographic factors
- 2) To study the correlation between behavior of the roasted coffee consumer and behavior trend for the roasted coffee consumer at petrol station on the route of Rangsit to Nakhon Nayok
- 3) To study the relationship between the attitude of the marketing mix and behavior trend for roasted coffee in petrol station on the route of Rangsit to Nakhon Nayok
- 4) To study the correlation between motivation of buying and behavior trend for roasted coffee in petrol station on the route of Rangsit to Nakhon Nayok

B. Research Hypotheses

- 1) The different in demographic of consumers at the petrol station on the route of Rangsit to Nakhon Nayok have different behavior trends for roast coffee consumers.
- 2) The behavior of roast coffee consumers correlates with the behavior trend of roasted coffee consumers on the route of Rangsit to Nakhon Nayok
- 3) Attitude of the marketing mix correlates with the behavior trend of roasted coffee consumer on the route of Rangsit to Nakhon Nayok
- 4) Motivation for selecting has a relationship with the behavior trend of roasted coffee consumers on the route of Rangsit to Nakhon Nayok

C. Research Framework

Research framework was drawn from many researches and from many high impact papers which offer very interesting theories of marketing mix [4]. In addition, Modern Market Management written by Siriwan Serirat and team (2003) and Behavioral trend from Schiffman and Kanuk (Schiffman, L.G. & Kanuk, 1994) has been applied in this research framework. [5], [6].

The population for this study was the roasted coffee consumers at petrol stations on the route of Rangsit to Nakhon Nayok.

D. Samples

The sample of this research was the roasted coffee consumer at 6 petrol stations on the route of Rangsit to Nakhon Nayok, for which are 385 sampling and a back up of 15 samplings all totally 400 samples.

The six petrol stations selected for collecting samples are:

1. Roasted coffee parlor “Coffee Boy” at Bangchak Petrol Station (First Klong)

2. Roasted coffee parlor “Coffee Manier” at Shell Petrol Station (Second Klong)
3. Roasted coffee parlor “Coffee Plus” at Caltex Petrol Station (Third Klong)
4. Roasted coffee parlor “Bann Rai Ka Fare” at Jet Petrol Station (Sixth Klong)
5. Roasted coffee parlor “Bann Rai Ka Fare” at PTT Petrol Station (Seventh Klong)
6. Roasted coffee parlor “Ka Fare Tha Pha Chan” at Bangchak Petrol Station (Eighth Klong)

E. Methods of Sampling

1. A quota sampling is used for 6 roasted coffee parlors
2. A convenient sampling is used by distributing the questionnaire to random customers at the 6 selected roasted coffee parlors.

III. FINDINGS

The finding of this research revealed that the respondents were male, mostly 33-39 years old, second 26-32 years old and third 40-46 years old. The majority of respondents had a bachelor degree and higher bachelor's degree and diploma education level respectively. In terms of occupations, most were private business proprietors, entrepreneurs, second government officer, state enterprise, and private company officer. Their monthly income was 10,000-16,000 Thai baht, second over 28,000 Thai baht, and monthly income of less or equal 10,000 Thai baht. These consumers had maximum drink expense at 300 Thai baht and minimum at 45 Thai baht per day. Maximum 42 cups per week and minimum 7 cup per week was reported. Consumers preferred to drink in the afternoon and often choose to buy ice coffee. The popular coffee item was cappuccino in which the taste is bitter. Roasted coffee parlor “Bann Rai Ka Fare” at Jet Petrol Station (Sixth Klong) was the best seller. For the marketing mix, consumers were in very good attitude and good motivation when their drink. The factor of return to buy and recommended the service to others were rated as high.

The hypothesis testing revealed medium correlations between behaviors of consume per time/per week with the trend of return to buy and recommended the service to others. This can be explained that the consumption per time and per week had increased, therefore, consumers tend to return to buy and recommended the service to others. Beside this, the attitude to marketing mix had medium correlations between behavior trends of returning and recommended to others. When coffee roasted consumers had high motivation, they tended to had high in return to buy and recommended the service to others.

IV. DISCUSSION

1. The analysis of correlating behavior and behavioral trend of the roasted coffee consumers found that the spending behavior and quantity of consumption had effects to returning of buying and recommended the service to others, which is consistent with Orawan R. (2004) [7].

The finding of her study discovered that the behavior of spending and quantity per week correlated with behavioral trend of returning of buying and recommended the service to others. The findings indicated the Loyalty Customer.

2. This study of correlation between the marketing mix and behavioral trend in returning of service and recommended the service to others, indicated over all attitude had a significance in Statistic, which concurred with Orawan R. (2004) [7]. The findings of her study revealed that the behavioral trend of decision-making. The research indicated the attitude of marketing mix had associated with returning of services and recommended the service to others
3. The study of motivation of selecting roasted coffee and behavioral trend of consumer in returning of services and recommended the service to others was concurred with Phusadee W. (2003) [8] who studies production factors that affected green tea consumer in Bangkok. The finding of the research indicated the motivation had an effect on green tea consumer in Bangkok.

V.SUGGESTIONS

1. The attitude of roasted coffee consumer with marketing mixes in product and behavior of returning services had correlated therefore this aspect can be the strong point of Roasted coffee parlor business on the route of Rangsit to Nakhon Nayok. The entrepreneur should consider the material for instance, the coffee bean, variety of favor, and quality of coffee bean. This will increase behavioral trend in returning of service and recommended the service to others. Moreover, the motivation had a medium correlation; the entrepreneurs should advertise about the benefits of coffee for example refreshing, heal thirstiness, taste and aroma of coffee.
2. The majority of consumers were male, the aged of 33-39 years old with the bachelor's degree and prefer bitter coffee, rich, sweet taste with ice. The estimate consuming was average 20 cups per week. The entrepreneur can use this data for create marketing plan for specific target group.
3. The research found the attitude of customer ranked in very good state. The entrepreneur should keep improving the quality of product and consider about the seasoning to meet needs of customer. This can develop the business and branding to become well know in this industry.
4. The selling indicated that roasted coffee parlor operating in petrol stations on the route of Rangsit to Nakhon Nayok was limited by only traveling customers or petrol filling customers. Therefore, there should be comfortable parking and ease of purchase.

REFERENCES

- [1] S. Kanmune. How well do you know about coffee?, Bangkok: Dokyah, 2003.
- [2] Kasikorn Bank Research Center. 2001.

- [3] W. Kritsakorn, "Thailand Tour with "Guru" Nakhon Nayok." (Second published). Bangkok: documentary under Virayahtharakit, 2001.
- [4] P. Kotler, "Marketing Management". Millennium Edition: Prentice Hall, 2003.
- [5] S. Serirut, et al., "Modern Marketing Management,,"Bangkok: Thamasarn, 2003.
- [6] L.G. Shiffman and L.L. Kanuk, "Consumer Behavior," New Jersey: Prentice -Hall, 1994.
- [7] R. Orawan, "Expectation and behavioral trend to roasted coffee consumer, route Bangkok to Petchaburi". Master of Business Administration, Marketing, Srinakarin Viroth University, 2004.
- [8] W. Phusadee, "Production factors that affect green tea consumer in Bangkok". Master of Business Administration, Marketing, Srinakarin Viroth University, 2003.